

Supporting Information

Tailoring the Shape Memory Properties of Segmented Poly(ester urethanes) via Blending

*Anuja Shirole, Carlo U. Perotto, Sandor Balog, and Christoph Weder**

Adolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, 1700 Fribourg,
Switzerland

**Corresponding author. Email: christoph.weder@unifr.ch*

Figure S1. TGA traces, recorded at a heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, of the neat PBA-PU and its blends with 10, 20, and 30% w/w PBA.

Figure S2. DSC traces, recorded at heating/cooling rates of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, showing the 2nd heating and cooling cycles of neat PBA. The numbers indicate the maxima of the melting/crystallization peaks.

Figure S3. WAXS spectra of the neat PBA (a), the neat PBA-PU (b), and PBA-PU/PBA blends with 10% w/w (c) 20% w/w (d) and 30% w/w (e) PBA, respectively. In each case, a function representing a linear combination of a quadratic function interpreting the amorphous halo, and Gaussian functions interpreting the Bragg-reflections from the crystal planes was fit against the spectra.

Figure S4. (a) SAXS spectra of the neat PBA, PBA-PU and 10, 20, or 30% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blends. (b) SAXS/WAXS spectra of the neat PBA, AcPBA and 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA blend. (c) SAXS and (d) WAXS spectra of the neat PCL, PBA-PU and 10, 20, or 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL blends.

Figure S5. Size-exclusion chromatography traces of the neat PBA-PU, PCL, and 10, 20 or 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL mixtures.

Figure S6. DSC traces showing the first heating (a) and the first cooling cycles (b) of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixture prepared by solvent casting, a solvent-cast 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA film that had been re-molded in a hot press, and a 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixture prepared by melt mixing. (c) Size-exclusion chromatography traces of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixture prepared by solvent casting, a solvent-cast 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA film that had been re-molded in a hot press, and a 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixture prepared by melt mixing at 180 °C.

Figure S7. (a) ^1H NMR (chloroform- d , 400 MHz) spectra of PBA and AcPBA showing the complete suppression of the triplet associated with the CH_2 adjacent to the terminal hydroxyl groups (3.65 ppm) and the appearance of the acetyl CH_3 singlet (2.04 ppm). (b) FTIR (ATR) spectra of PBA and AcPBA showing the absence of OH stretching band for the end-capped AcPBA. (c) Size-exclusion chromatography traces of PBA and AcPBA.

Figure S8. (a) Size-exclusion chromatograms of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA mixture made by melt-compounding, the neat PBA-PU processed with the same protocol, and the original (unmodified) PBA. (b) DSC traces showing the first and second heating and cooling cycles of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA mixture prepared by melt-mixing. (c) Isothermal DSC traces of the melt-mixed and solution-cast 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA mixtures and the melt-mixed 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA mixture; the traces were recorded after first heating the samples to 100 °C and cooling to 37 °C.

Figure S9. Shape memory tests (temperature-stress-strain cycles) of PBA-PU (a), 10% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (b), (c), (d) and 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA blend (e). The fixing temperature was 37°C (a), 20 °C (b), 25 °C (c), (d), and 30 °C (e). In each cycle, the sample was heated to 70 °C, maintained at 70 °C for 5 min, before the force was increased at a rate of $0.8 \text{ N} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ until the strain reached ca. 40%. The deformed samples were subsequently cooled under constant stress to the desired fixing temperature, where the stress was maintained for 5 (b, c, e), 15 (d) or 30 min (a). The applied stress was then removed and the samples were kept at the fixing temperature for another 5 min. Finally, the samples were heated to 70 °C and this temperature was maintained for 10 min to promote shape recovery.

Figure S10. Shape memory tests (temperature-stress-strain cycles) of the 20% w/w PBA-PU/AcPBA (a) and the 20% w/w PBA-PU/PBA solution cast blend (b). The fixing temperature was 37 °C. In each cycle, the sample was heated to 70 °C, maintained at 70 °C for 5 min, before the force was increased at a rate of 0.8 N·min⁻¹ until the strain reached ca. 40%. The deformed samples were subsequently cooled under constant stress to 37 °C and kept at this temperature for 30 min, before the applied stress was removed and the samples were kept for another 5 min at this temperature. Finally, the samples were heated to 70 °C and this temperature was maintained for 10 min to promote shape recovery.

Figure S11. Shape memory tests (temperature-stress-strain cycles) of the 30% w/w PBA-PU/PCL mixture. The fixing temperature was 37 °C. All cycles were programmed by heating the sample to 70 °C, maintaining it at 70 °C for 5 min before, the force was increased at a rate of 0.8 N·min⁻¹ until the strain reached ca. 40%. The deformed sample was subsequently cooled under constant stress to 37 °C and kept at this temperature for 30 min. The applied stress was removed and the sample was kept at this stage for another 5 min to adopt the temporary shape. Finally, the samples were heated to 70 °C and this temperature was maintained for 10 min to promote shape recovery.